

Low-Cost Optical Camera Communications for IoT

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Abstract—Visible light communication (VLC) based on an optical camera system is a promising technology for indoor IoT applications. It offers advantages such as reduced interference and improved performance but also suffers from limited data rate transmission due to the fixed capture rate of an image sensor. This study aims to address this limitation by integrating multiple low-cost CMOS sensors with precise synchronization to receive successive data bits. The paper presents the design of a cost-effective functional prototype implementation of a multi-spatial receiver consisting of multiple image sensors capable of providing a continuous data rate of 500 bps with a theoretical aggregated receive rate of 1.6 Mbps. The system performance is evaluated under varying indoor lighting conditions and distances. The proposed system demonstrates its effectiveness for indoor IoT optical communications. Furthermore, the use of several cameras makes it feasible to provide location capabilities without requiring additional hardware or complex algorithms.

Index Terms—Optical camera-based VLC, Internet of Things, low-cost system, optical wireless communication, visible light positioning

I. INTRODUCTION

The growing congestion on electromagnetic spectrum bands results in a scarcity of available bandwidth making it challenging to accommodate the surging demand for Internet connectivity and requiring additional resources either from the hardware or the network infrastructure. This rapid shift towards a more connected world and the overcrowding of available bandwidth has captured the attention of researchers. In response to this current congestion of Radio Frequency (RF) bands researchers are exploring various alternatives, including the use of visible light technology.

Visible Light Communication (VLC) is a strong contender that utilizes a broad unregulated visible light spectrum and is considered an alternative to RF communications [1]. In VLC, where the transmitter (Tx) is always a source of light, two types of receivers (Rxs) could be used, namely Photodiode (PD) and Image sensors (ISs) or cameras. VLC with photodiode as the receiver has been widely investigated in the literature for indoor environments [2], [3]. PDs are capable of providing high-speed data transmission but may face challenges when used for longer link spans. The optical signal that travels over extended distances experiences signal attenuation leading to a weaker signal at the receiver end. Secondly, interference from ambient light due to its extremely sensitive nature results in a reduction of the data transmission accuracy. Filtering techniques could be used to reduce interference. However, certain environments with high

light intensity might still pose challenges for accurate data transmission, leading to signal noise and lower overall system performance. Contrarily, VLC with image sensor, also referred to as Optical Camera Communications (OCC), is endorsed by both industry and commerce [4]. Besides simultaneous data transmission and optical vision, it offers distinctive features: compatibility with user devices such as smartphones and mobile robots, and improved performance under ambient light [5]. Unlike photodiode-based VLC, which only acquires color and intensity, the Optical Camera-based VLC (OC-VLC) system uses image sensors as a receiver to acquire data in the form of 2D image sequences. As a result, it is able to transmit more information that could be useful for communication as well as localization [6] applications. Given this popularity and intrinsic benefits, OC-VLC is considered to be an intriguing wireless technology in the growing Internet of Things within the context of 5G wireless networks. It is essential for many mobile robot applications in industrial environments [7], provides a broad range of services such as augmented reality, robotic planning and navigation with a lightweight and cost-effective solution, strong data security along with a compelling substitute to high-cost industrial laser and RF-denied interior environments [8].

Furthermore, OC-VLC along with the LED technology also provides exceptional precision in an Indoor Positioning System (IPS). These IPSs leverage the capability of the LED to transmit unique identifiers or coordinate information, which is then decoded by a camera at the receiving end to determine its relative position and orientation to the LED source. The Optical Camera-based Visible Light Positioning (OC-VLP) offers a range of benefits when compared to RF-based alternatives like RFID, WiFi, and Bluetooth technologies. These advantages encompass exceptional precision in positioning, immunity to electromagnetic interference, and the simultaneous capability to perform positioning and illumination tasks. Moreover, OC-VLP surpasses most RF-based positioning technologies by achieving accuracy within the centimeter range.

However, the optical-based systems also exhibit certain limitations and drawbacks in which most cameras have fixed frame rates thus limiting the bit rate transmission of the system. To obtain flicker free VLC connection the frequency of transmitted light must be greater than the human eye's critical flicker frequency (CFF) i.e. 90 Hz [9]. For most of the cameras including digital single-lens reflex and commercial smartphone built-in cameras, their frame rate typically does

not exceed 60 frames per second [10]. Ke-Ling Hsu [11] used iPhone 7 plus as a VLC receiver to capture signal at 30 fps over a 1.5 m transmission range. Cahyadi [12] worked on a downlink camera-based VLC system that utilizes an 8 x 8 LED matrix and allows rotation compensation to receive data at a different angle using a smartphone. The author in [13] presented a multi-input multi-output nonlinear of sight optical communication system that uses two white LEDs and an Honor 30 Sony IMX600 with 60 fps as a receiver. The received frames were processed offline through MATLAB to retrieve transmitted data. Therefore, these low frame rate camera systems are not fast enough to capture every symbol in a data stream with a data rate higher than CFF.

As an attempt to address this issue, a few studies reported in literature use high-cost high-resolution cameras, such as GoPro Hero 6 for optical correlation algorithms to identify pixels and unique ID of LED and to locate LED emitters on images [14], Thorslab BU238M with 165 fps for computer vision based VLC assisted indoor localization algorithm [15].

This article proposes an OCC system using multi-camera synchronization, for practical and accurate data transmission in indoor environments. The main contribution of this paper is the development of a low-cost system by integrating multiple cost-effective CMOS cameras in such a way that each camera captures one after another taking successive data bits from the transmitter. The system effectively utilizes the processing time of one camera to activate the next camera to enhance the overall frame rate. Furthermore, the proposed system serves as the basis for a positioning and localization framework. However, it is important to note that the focus of this research is primarily on the development of a low-cost VLC system and efficient data transmission in indoor environments. While the potential for leveraging the OC-VLC system for positioning and localization is recognized, further exploration and implementation of such functionalities are left for future investigation.

To this end besides this introduction and background, the paper contains four sections as follows: Section II gives an overview of system design covering key aspects such as camera synchronization, detailed insight into the image sensor's operation, frame timing calculation of the rolling shutter camera, and presents the proposed experimental testbed design. Section III analyze system performance in terms of bit error rate at different distances and varying light intensities. Section IV concludes the paper and outlines potential future directions for further research and improvements in the system.

II. SYSTEM DESIGN OVERVIEW

In optical-based VLC transmission system data is modulated by a processor using a modulation technique and sent to the receiver through a light source. A CMOS sensor at the receiver captures the light states, which, once processed and demodulated provide the transmitted bits. Figure 1 shows a block diagram of the VLC process.

At the transmitter, the processor generates binary data and encodes the signal through the On-Off Keying (OOK) modu-

Fig. 1. VLC process diagram.

Fig. 2. Proposed VLC system.

lation technique converting '0' to '0' and '1' to '1' while an off-the-shelf LED luminaire mounted on the ceiling provides illumination and broadcasts modulated signals through light waves. The light signals are then reflected by a retroreflector on the opposite end, directing them toward the receiver. On the receiver side, multiple low-cost cameras (also mounted on the ceiling) work as a single receiver unit to decode data transmitted from the emitter. Figure 2 illustrates the scenario of the proposed optical camera-based VLC system.

A. Synchronization

In a distributed system, the time deviation is mainly due to each device having its own hardware clock which is independent of the other devices. Ensuring precise time synchronization in a multi-camera system is essential, the fact that each device operates at its own independent time makes the synchronization necessary. To keep the cameras synchronized an external trigger is used after a specific time to initialize all the cameras one after the other at every 2ms as shown in Figure 3.

B. Image Sensor

All the cameras are configured with identical sensor settings (i.e. resolution, quality, exposure time, etc.) and are programmed in a similar manner. Upon receiving the synchronization trigger from the external clock, each camera initializes and undergoes light exposure to sequentially read the pixels in a row-by-row manner as shown in Figure 4. To optimize data transfer speed and avoid slower serial peripheral interfaces, we utilize the internal RAM for storing the image data instead of an external flash. The captured data is saved in a compressed RGB format with each color taking one byte, and then stored in a buffer for future processing. Consequently, the size of the RAW image (without compression) is calculated

Fig. 3. Camera synchronization.

Fig. 4. Row-by-row exposure

by multiplying the number of pixels by 3. Subsequently, the jpg file is decompressed to extract information from the 2D images. Finally, a threshold is applied to the resulting image to determine the LED state. The workflow of the image sensor is illustrated in Figure 5. The entire process of capturing, storing, and processing takes less than 20 milliseconds, resulting in an individual capture rate of 50 fps and a combined rate of 500 fps with ten cameras.

C. Frame Time

The time required to read a complete image depends on the total number of rows and pixels per row. A frame with 400x300 resolution consists of 300 lines (rows) of active pixels plus additional lines for vertical blanking as shown in Figure 6 [16]. Provided a 36 MHz pixel clock frequency, the time for one line (LTime) can be computed as follows:

$$LTime = \frac{400 \text{ pixels} + 195 \text{ pixels of horizontal blanking}}{36 \text{ MHz}} = 16.53 \mu\text{s}$$

The total frame time (FTime) is derived by multiplying LTime by the number of lines in the frame, which includes both active lines and vertical blanking:

$$FTime = (\text{numLines} + \text{tFrameblank}) \times LTime$$

$$FTime = (300 \text{ lines} + 36 \text{ lines of vertical blanking}) \times 16.53 \mu\text{s} = 5.554 \text{ ms}$$

Fig. 5. Workflow of camera

Fig. 6. Frame Timing

Fig. 7. Actual Setup

Fig. 8. LED pixel coordinates

Assuming the same number of vertical and horizontal blanking the frame time for 160x120 resolution is 1.52 ms.

$$1.52 \text{ ms} \times 13 = 19.76 \text{ ms} < 20 \text{ ms}$$

To this end, 20 ms timing between consecutive images from the same camera, allows the integration of up to thirteen cameras without time overlap.

D. Proposed System

Figure 7 illustrates the physical arrangement of the experimental setup, showcasing different viewpoints captured by each camera. By determining the pixel coordinates (x, y) within the frame that contain LED landmark information, we are able to identify the transmitted data bits. To this end, the system with ten cameras is capable of achieving 500 bits per second by making use of a single LED occupying an area of 2×3 pixels in the image. However, with spatial multiplexing and utilizing each spatial channel with individual light sources across the entire region of the image, the potential reception rate increases to over 1.6 Mbps. So, by fully exploiting the system's potential, it is possible to significantly enhance performance and achieve faster data transmission rates.

Additionally, leveraging information of pixel coordinates along the known relative distance and orientations of the cameras can enable precise depth estimation of the object in three-dimensional space, as demonstrated in Figure 9.

Fig. 9. Object Positioning

TABLE I
EXPERIMENTAL SETUP PARAMETERS

Parameters	Values
Camera Chip	OV2640
Resolution	160x120
Frame Rate	50 frames per second
Interval	20 ms
Test Distance	60 cm to 250 cm
Ambient Illumination Level	500 lux
Illumination LED1 (L1)	5 mm, 3.14 V, 20 mA
Illumination LED2 (L2)	8 mm, 3.2 V, 30 mA

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

To analyze the performance of the proposed system we carried out a series of experiments. These experiments were aimed at validating the effectiveness and reliability in terms of receiving accurate data. Figure 7 displays the actual experimental setup with ten cameras. Table 1 displays the various parameters of the setup, which were carefully chosen to ensure the appropriateness of the experimental conditions.

A. Analysis of BER to Distance

This test aims to determine the effect on received data by varying the height Distance (D) parameter. Multiple trials were taken to evaluate system performance by transmitting data sequences and systematically varying D between the Tx and Rx. Table II shows the measured Bit Error Ratio (BER) values obtained for LEDs L1 and L2 of 5 mm and 8 mm diameter respectively. As depicted, the BER for L1 and L2 is in the range of 10^{-4} for $60 < D < 230\text{cm}$, and for $D < 230\text{cm}$ we observed gradual degradation in the received signal quality for L1. This is due to the reduced received pixel values. However, D could be increased using a LED larger, moving from a diameter of 5 mm to 50 mm.

TABLE II
DISTANCE VS BIT ERROR RATIO

Distance (D)	BER (with L1)	BER (with L2)
60 cm	$10^{-4} \times 0.6$	$10^{-4} \times 0.3$
120 cm	$10^{-4} \times 1$	$10^{-4} \times 0.3$
170 cm	$10^{-4} \times 1.3$	$10^{-4} \times 0.6$
200 cm	$10^{-4} \times 5.6$	$10^{-4} \times 1.6$
230 cm	$10^{-4} \times 7.6$	$10^{-4} \times 2.3$
250 cm	$10^{-3} \times 0.3$	$10^{-4} \times 3.6$

Fig. 10. BER vs Illumination (lux)

B. Analysis of BER to Light Intensity

In an indoor environment, multiple light sources are usually used to provide sufficient illumination. As per the ISO 8995-1 standard, it is recommended to have an illumination level not lower than 500 lux for an indoor office space [17]. We evaluate system performance by incorporating additional LED panels other than the Tx to enhance the lux level. The BER of the system is measured with increasing light intensity. Figure 8 shows the results at (i) 180 degrees: when both the VLC receiver and light panels are mounted on the ceiling facing to the ground (ii) 90 degrees: when the VLC receiver is mounted on the ceiling and external light coming from room window making 90-degrees the receiver.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This work addresses the challenge associated with limited data rate transmission in VLC systems due to fixed image sensor capture rates. The integration of multiple low-cost CMOS sensors with precise synchronization enhances the transmission rate. The implementation of ten cameras, a single LED-emitting IoT device, and simple OOK modulation allows the system to achieve a continuous data rate of 500 bps. However, with spatial multiplexing, the transmission rate reaches 1.6 Mbps. The effectiveness of the system is validated under different illumination levels and at various distances in an indoor environment.

Several directions have been identified as future work. Firstly, the system will be extended for mobile robot position and localization applications, it is also possible to use smart tags that can be identified and located using the cameras. Secondly, the performance of the system will be further improved by using more sophisticated color-based modulation techniques and synchronization algorithms. Lastly, while the current solution corresponds to the uplink transmission, the downlink will be implemented using a LED panel and a photodiode on the IoT device.

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